

RETENTION TO THE PROGRAM IMPLEMENTATION LEVEL IN SPORTS BASED ON THE DEPED ORDER NO. 25 S. 2015: THE CASE OF GENERAL SANTOS CITY NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL

RUDYLITO L. BOBOROL, GERALDINE D. RODRIGUEZ, EdD,

NOE P. GARCIA, RGC, PhD

Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges

Graduate School

Pioneer Avenue, General Santos City, Philippines

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Abstract: The researcher wanted to identify the retention to the program implementation level in the sports based on the DepEd Order no. 25 s. 2015 in GSCHNS, and the data would be the basis for making the intervention program. The researcher utilized the quantitative research method more specifically, the quantitative evaluative design. The collected data were based on the result given by all student-athletes of GSCNHS on the survey questionnaire as a tool where the questionnaire was based on DepEd Order N. 25 S. 2015. The data were analyzed and interpreted using an appropriate statistical tool which was a weighted mean. Based on the result, the retention to the program implementation level in sports was high. Despite the result, still the proponent formulated an intervention program to sustain or improve the retention of the respondents in the chosen program.

Keywords: Retention to the program implementation level in sports, DepEd order no. 25 s. 2015, guidance and counselling, Philippines.

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the furthestmost significant challenges facing student-athletes is the time required to blend the functions of being a student and athlete. Student-athletes participate in a competitive sport sponsored by an educational institution to which they are registered. They are generally required to balance the roles of being full-time students and at the same time being athletes. They must commit a large extent of additional time to their athletic events and regular classwork with the athletic demands. Regardless of being an athlete and having practiced for the most part, student-athletes must enter classes and obtain a passing grade (Baker & Wattie, 2018; Gilson & Sturm, 2016).

Furthermore, student-athletes represent an identifiable and unique population. While student-athletes confront many of the same issues as non-athletes, their dual roles can compound the challenges that all college students face. Regular physical activity has been linked to improved academic achievement, higher GPAs, and improved brain function (Coxe et al., 2018; Geltz, 2017; Pohle-Krauza & Roddy, 2017).

Through the years, GSCNHS were undefeated at the division level. The school provided student-athletes to compete in the region to the national level in sports. The program is one of the reasons why some students want to enroll in GSCNHS. The

implementing guidelines of the Special Program in Sports emphasized that for student-athletes to stay in the program they need to meet the requirements during their stay, specifically by maintaining a passing grade of 85% and above in their field of discipline, while not less than 80 % in all other subject areas. It is also important that the student-athlete will not incur more than 20% absences in the total number of school days (DepEd Order n. 25 s. 2015).

The failure to fully implement the retention program in the past has had crucial implications for achieving the program objectives and fairness in comfort delivery. One possible reason for the poor results was that, despite the many new and more complex problems now facing the admin, the strategies used by the administrators for seeking solutions have hardly changed or do not just match the increasing difficulty of the retention issues. Another reason was that designing the guidelines the way admin thinks they should be and once designed, seldom run as they were supposed to (Rowe, Schulenkorf & Sherry, 2016).

Consequently, implementations issues have even greater urgency as guidelines are now entrusted from the DepEd national to school through delegations. The new delegated development method entails public engagement in determining priorities, allocating resources to accomplish them, and guaranteeing that schools are economically empowered. The cost of recruiting and training for the sports program will climb if students do not stay in the program. (Brown, 2019; Pestano et al., 2021; Pont and Viennet, 2017).

In response to this situation, the researcher would like to zoom in on the retention to the program implementation level in sports based on the DepEd Order n. 25 s. 2015 and come up with a relevant intervention program that would strengthen the status of the Sports Program.

Statement of the Problem

1. Based on the DepEd order n 25 s. 2015, what is the retention to the program implementation level in sport of GSCNHS?
2. What intervention can be drawn based on the outcome of the study?

Conceptual Framework

The Conceptual Framework below presents the direction of the study. The upper box shows retention to the program implementation level in sports based on the DepEd Order N. 25, S. 2015, while the lower box would be the intervention program formulated.

The degree to which the retention policy is implemented may impact the number of student-athletes who are retained in the sports program. Failure to retain students may increase costs in the recruitment and training of new incumbents for the sports program.

The proposed intervention program was formulated based on the result of the study. This intervention program will somehow help increase the number of student-athletes enrolled in the Special Program in Sports.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of the Study

Theoretical Framework

The foundation of this research was the theory of the development Through Sport by Mathew T. Bowers and Christine Green (2016).

The Olympic and professional sports landscapes are, without a doubt, more competitive than ever before. Winning sporting competitions has significant financial and commercial benefits like Olympic Gold or even avoiding relegation to English Premier League football means vast resources are invested within national governing bodies and professional sports clubs to achieve success (Jones, Weaving, Tee, Darral-Jones, & Weakley, 2018)

One approach center on recognizing and creating early athletic ability into the donning whizzes of tomorrow. This framework, commonly known as an Ability Recognizable proof and Advancement Framework (ARPAF), has altogether developed inside the final 15–20 a long time and regularly reflects impressive money-related venture. Sports development has become a significant problem for sports policymakers and sports managers worldwide (Cobley et al., 2018; Scantlebury et al., 2017).

Sports development systems have two primary goals: to increase the number of students who participate in sports and to improve the quality of their performances. These are the basis of the much-used but seldom studied pyramid equivalence in sports development. The article” Building Sports Program to Optimize Athlete Recruitment, Retention and Transition” found out the pyramid ideal of sport development and evaluated its basic expectations. It identifies three responsibilities essential for a concrete pyramid model: athlete recruitment, athlete retention, and athlete transitions (Bowers, 2016; Green, 2016; Lavallee & Rea, 2017).

2. METHODOLOGY

The researcher used the quantitative evaluative design, a form of quantitative research. According to Creswell (2013), a quantitative method includes data gathering, analyzing, interpreting, and putting the study results down. Sample and design were directed tools in this approach. Unusual methods are accessible in both survey and experimental studies that direct behavior with the factors named in the problems above. More specifically, this research used a descriptive, evaluative design. According to Calmorin (2016), descriptive, evaluative research seeks to appraise or assess in some way, providing beneficial information about something new than might be gathered in usual observation or inquiry of relationships. This method of research includes interviews and mailed questionnaires. In a quantitative field study or observation, they employ a tool to gather data.

The locale of the research is General Santos City National High School. One of the schools implementing the SPS program in Region 12 is located at Rizal Street, Barangay Calumpang, General Santos City. This school was one of the leading schools that produced student-athletes who would represent the region in national sports events.

The researcher used the survey tool to gather the needed data. Items were based on the DepEd Order No. 25. s. of 2015. Taken from the DepEd Order, the survey tool underwent thorough validation by the expert validators.

Before being utilized to collect data from his respondents, the survey questionnaire was content validated with the assistance of specialists. Three expert validators were chosen based on their knowledge and the study's research methods. The following criteria were used to validate it: (1) clarity of directions and items; (2) presentation/organization of items; (3) suitability of items; (4) adequateness item category; (5) attainment of the purpose; (6) each item requires only the specific answer of measures only behavior, and no aspect of the questionnaire suggests a bias of the researcher; (7) scale and evaluation rating system.

The data collection procedure of this study involved letter of permission, and letter of participation. The researcher primarily sent a letter of request for approval to conduct the study to the General Santos City Division addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent. When the request for approval was signed, the researcher sent a letter addressed to the school principals of the school. The researcher provided a copy of the letter approved by the School Principal to the SPS Program Coordinator, the class advisers, and the teacher-trainers.

The researcher personally conducted or administered the survey tool to the respondents to gather the needed data.

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Furthermore, Moreover, the weighted mean was used as a statistical tool to analyze the research data. The data were categorized as Strongly Agree, Agree, Moderately Agree, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree using a survey instrument as a research tool.

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

Findings

Table 1 presents the level of the retention program implementation of Special Program in Sports of General Santos City National High School 2020-2021. The data were analyzed and interpreted using a weighted mean.

Table 1: Retention to the Program Implementation Level in Sports Based on the DepEd Order NO. 25 S. of 2015

Indicators	x	Student- Athletes (N-429)	
		Description	Interpretation
A. ACADEMICS			
To be retained in the program, a student shall:			
1. Atleast approaching Proficiency (80%-84%) level in all other subjects. In cases where the above requirement was not met, a student be accepted in the regular program, provided he/she is not at the Beginning level in any learning area.	3.82	Agree	High
2. Absences must not incur more than 20% of the total number of school days	3.80	Agree	High
B. SPORTS SPECIALIZATION			
To be retained in the program, a student shall:			
1. Maintain a Proficient (85%-89%) level of assessment in the specialized subject.	4.05	Agree	High
2. Maintain physical and mental fitness	4.26	Strongly Agree	Very High
C. BEHAVIOR			
To be retained in the program, student shall:			
1. Exhibit good behavior at all times	4.35	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall	4.06	Agree	High

The overall mean score was 4.06, with the corresponding qualitative description as *Agree* as indicated in the table. This signifies that the level of the retention program implementation of the particular program in sports is high. To put it in another way, the students had met the academic requirements to be retained in the program. They had at least an approaching Proficiency (80%-84%) level in all subject areas. However, other students who failed to meet the first condition had academic performance, not at the Beginning level in any learning area. Additionally, the students did not incur absences more than 20 % of the total number of school days.

The result convincingly portrayed that the level of the retention program implementation of a particular program in sports is high. The result indeed denoted that the student-athletes could meet the different provisions (requirements) prescribed to be retained in the sports program.

The result of this study is pleasing to note. While maintaining good behavior, student-athletes balance their performances between sports specialization and academics precisely. The implementation of the program is excellent, if not exceptional. The result also can be attributed to the excellent leadership of the sports coordinator and, of course, the untiring efforts of the dedicated teachers under the sports program.

As a result, the respondents' support for school athletics increased as their academic achievement improved (Garcia & Subia, 2019). At all levels of competition, student-athletes must meet academic requirements while also balancing their athletic and academic responsibilities (Hendricks, 2016). Considerable proof recommends that student-athletes who participate in academic support programs advantage academically. The GPA of the high school examinations was the sole basis on which college admission decisions were taken. With GPA having primary suggestions on the status of a student at the institution, effective integration into excellent academic practices is vital for student victory.

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Moreover, an issue of concern in higher education institutions worldwide is the retention and success of students. Typically, a particularly pressing issue within the setting of extending participation for under-represented student groups, increasing student differences, and instructive quality confirmation and responsibility forms (Heagney, 2016).

In addition, retention may be very challenging, but numerous times disregarded organization within the process. Holding and conceivably expanding the inclusion of people requires an in-depth investigation of what influences their choice to remain. Most consideration must be given to specific perspectives which empower advanced interest, such as giving more preparing openings, support to development, and adaptability in enrollment choices (Grima et al., 2017).

Furthermore, while retention can be difficult, it is frequently overlooked as a part of the process. Retaining and conceivably expanding the association of people requires an in-depth analysis of what affects their decision to stay. Retention has become one of the main student-related problems in schools today due to the influence of parents on the student's decision during enrolment (Dalangin, 2021).

Poor preparation, a poor course or specialization match resulting in a lack of commitment, a lack of social integration, and personal circumstances are all reasons or categories why students leave the program, according to a synthesis of research on student retention conducted by Heagney (2016).

Proposed Intervention Program

Based on the study findings, an intervention program/s could somehow reach the very high level of the retention program implementation of the special program in sports. Therefore, creating a registration advocacy campaign that can assist students-athletes can register and stay in the program until they graduate.

In view thereof, the researcher developed an activity as an intervention program with an activity title, ENROLLMENT AND RETENTION ADVOCACY CAMPAIGN. The goal of the project design is to increase the number of student-athletes in the SPS program, sustain the retention implementation, increase participation in different sports competitions and attain sustainable Program Plans and Activities of Sports

The special sports program's retention program is excellent. Academically, the students had fulfilled the requirements for continued enrollment in the program. This intervention is intended to supplement the current program.

The activity targets 83 participants which includes the public-school teachers and school heads through a virtual conferencing via Google Meet. Resource speakers from the field of financial literacy and wellness will be invited to discuss the different considerations in attaining a sound financial well-being and realize the aforementioned objectives of the activity.

4. CONCLUSIONS

For over a decade, a special program in sports has been implemented in General Santos City National High School, students' output in athletic meets has a very satisfactory. In contrast, the retention of student-athletes has been remarkably alarming. Under the SPS program, there has also been a continuous decrease in student retention.

The retention program implementation of a special program in sports of GSCNHS is high. Hence, the student-athletes could meet the different provisions (requirements) prescribed to be retained in the sports program. They reached a nice balance between academics and sports specialization while maintaining a positive attitude. The program is well-executed. Gencer and Öztürks emphasized that Sports programs designed with vivid implementing regulations would lead to positive outcomes in sports performance among student-athletes. While coaches served as models and channels to student-athlete's sports developments, their actions and expectations remained on the admissible process of gradual yet intensive training of their student-athletes.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the data, the level of retention implementation is high and conclusions drawn. Implementors of the sports program can devise their implementing guidelines to help the student-athlete's retention. Principals or sports administrators may ensure that the facilities and equipment are available for the development of the program. Teacher – trainers formulate a program on their own to help student-athletes retain in the program. Student-athletes must be informed about the DepEd order n. 25 s. 2015 which is the Implementing Guidelines of the Special Program in Sports. Design a strategy similar to the "Enrollment and Retention Advocacy Campaign" to recruit more student-athletes to enroll in Special Sports Programs.

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